

Beyond the land of the living death: early-stage transformational entrepreneurs in digital healthcare as liminality navigator

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Purpose – The Lean Startup Approach (LSA) is extensively utilized by early-stage entrepreneurs, with “pivot” serving as a key pillar. However, there is a research gap concerning the boundary conditions impacting LSA and pivot decisions, especially when addressing societal challenges, as in the context of transformational entrepreneurship. In this regard, the healthcare sector, further compounded by a lack of research on startups and scale-ups, presents an embraced opportunity to provide multiple contributions for both theory and practice.

Design/methodology/approach – The present investigation employs a grounded approach to explore the experiences of the co-founders of a fast-growing Italian e-health startup. A narrative strategy was employed to organize conditions and evolving strategic action/interactions into three different pivoting phases of the startup—before the pivot, its enactment and aftermath—with primary and secondary data collected over a period of one year.

Findings – Pivoting in digital healthcare unfolded as a liminal experience marked by factors such as high regulation, multiple stakeholders, technological and symbolic ambivalence, resource-intensive demands, and institutional actors acting as pathway pioneers, leading to an information overload and unforeseeable uncertainty to manage. These factors challenge entrepreneurs' ability to attain optimal distinctiveness, presenting the paradoxical need for vertical flexibility for scaling up.

Originality/value – This study introduces a process model of transformational information crafting when pivoting, highlighting the role of entrepreneurs' transformational stance and platform-mediated solutions as engines behind strategies involving information breaking and transition, preceding knowledge-driven integration strategies.

Social implications – By uniquely illuminating the sector's constraints on entrepreneurial phenomena, this study provides a valuable guide for entrepreneurs and institutional actors in addressing societal challenges.

Keywords Entrepreneurial Strategy, Healthcare, Information, Lean Startup, Pivot, Platform, Regulated Markets, Social Ventures; Transformational Entrepreneurship

Introduction

Startups are vital engines of innovation, economic growth, and transformative change, challenging norms, introducing novel ideas, and driving job creation and technological progress while often addressing crucial societal challenges. However, startup companies face in general a heightened vulnerability in high-regulated industrial markets, as they inherently struggle to establish legitimacy (Santos and Eisenhardt, 2009). This vulnerability is amplified in healthcare, where cultural and structural barriers like Government regulation (e.g., Miller and French, 2016; Schiavone and Simoni, 2019; Chakraborty et al., 2021; Aerts et al., 2023) have given rise to a compelling narrative within the digital realm of healthcare entrepreneurship, casting a daunting shadow over the landscape. By way of illustration, before the pandemic, a trade press article by Forbes boldly **claimed** that the common view is that “98% of digital health startups are the walking dead right now” (Chase, 2016).

While anecdotal evidence endures, the COVID-19 pandemic, local alliances, sustainable challenges and especially the digital transition were found to be the latest great enabler in healthcare (Apostolopoulos et al., 2022; Aerts et al., 2023; Mishra and Pandey, 2023). These enablers appear to have played a role in compelling regulators and health institutional actors to potentially enhance their evaluation and support for entrepreneurial responses, technological innovation, and market development (Schiavone and Vershinina, 2022). **Nonetheless**, despite their promising prospects, the **diverse** and contemporary transformations in the healthcare sector also generate a significant influx of novel and unpredictable information for early-stage founding teams. This, coupled with pre-existing informational challenges arising from the intricate nature of a highly regulated, multi-stakeholder, and complex environment, poses substantial hurdles.

Amidst a similar environmental uncertainty, early-stage founding teams may encounter significant difficulties at the **outset** of their ventures in **healthcare**; **particularly**, these challenges

stem from the absence of comprehensive information, the acquisition of which requires considerable time and effort (Gans et al., 2019; Leatherbee & Katila, 2020). To tackle this specific obstacle, a novel learning-oriented methodology, known as the lean startup approach (LSA) has gained prominence over the past decade, becoming one of the most widely adopted approaches among entrepreneurs, especially under high levels of environmental uncertainty (Leatherbee and Katila, 2019; Silva et al., 2021; Shepherd & Gruber, 2021). The LSA underscores the significance of experimentation through continual testing of novel ideas and prompt adaptation to evolving competitive dynamics or consumer preferences (e.g., Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010; Ries, 2011; Blank, 2013). The main key pillars of this approach are business model, treating ideas as hypotheses, developing "minimum viable products", refining hypotheses through external validation, and "pivoting" in response to rejection. The concept of pivot in *"The Lean Startup"* (Ries, 2011, p. 149) is defined as a "structured course correction designed to test a new fundamental hypothesis about product, strategy and engine of growth" within a venture. Following the publication of Ries' work, this concept has significantly permeated entrepreneurial discourse. The term "pivot" is increasingly employed to denote a wide array of strategic shifts made by various actors, ranging from individuals to organizations and institutions. In parallel, regarding the LSA, there is also growing attention from the academic community, with scholars emphasizing the opportunities arising from closing the academic-practitioner divide (e.g., Dushnitsky and Matusik, 2019; Shepherd and Gruber, 2021).

Unfortunately, the LSA "has largely been portrayed as a one-size-fits-all solution—its key assumptions subject to little rigorous empirical testing, and the possibility of critical boundary conditions ignored" (Leatherbee and Katila, 2020, p. 570). While the 'one size fits all' approach may be unsatisfactory, it simultaneously presents a significant opportunity for both theory and practice: entrepreneurs can leverage this opportunity to be more precise in their activities, and researchers can explore boundary conditions, e.g., how LSA differs in the initiation of social ventures addressing societal challenges (Shepherd and Gruber, 2021).

The healthcare sector distinguishes itself within entrepreneurial domains for a nuanced interplay of regulatory frameworks and ethical considerations, yet by placing a profound emphasis on addressing societal challenges and patient well-being. This desired outcome could be facilitated through novel and transformational entrepreneurial approaches, that extend the paradigm *–in contrast to conventional entrepreneurial approaches–* by proactively leveraging innovation and new technologies to address social challenges (Ratten and Jones, 2018; Maas et al., 2019; Troise et al., 2022; Jones et al., 2023). The proactive stance of transformational entrepreneurship can therefore complement the LSA in addressing sustainability objectives amidst the challenges posed by the healthcare environment.

Notwithstanding the growing interest and opportunities, entrepreneurship has garnered modest emphasis within the healthcare ecosystem and scholarly inquiry. Indeed, the literature on the topic is still scant and underdeveloped, especially for startups: there is limited understanding and studies of entrepreneurship available on the identity of the entrepreneurs in this particular sector, and on how they configure and develop startups and how they scale up their firms within this particular context (Schiavone and Vershina, 2022; Aerts et al., 2023). It is patently clear that over time the architecture of the healthcare system acted as an impediment to the creation of a fertile ecosystem for new startup and entrepreneurship, wherein individuals could effectively capitalize on opportunities within a competitive market (Philips and Garman, 2006; Schiavone and Vershina, 2022). In this context, however, it is also evident that we lack a more comprehensive understanding of the key and context-specific conditions that constrain entrepreneurs' actions. Matter-of-factly, the influence of the sector-specific characteristics in shaping the entrepreneurial phenomena (e.g., De Massis et al., 2018; Van Burg et al., 2022), as

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3 the influence of entrepreneurs' characteristics (e.g., Foss and Klein, 2012; Grimes, 2018) have
4 been largely neglected by literature in the context of healthcare.

5 Along these lines, for what concerns entrepreneurship and digital platforms in healthcare,
6 previous literature further underscores that both scholarly research and industry
7 implementation have fallen behind in the healthcare sector (e.g., Hermes et al., 2020). The
8 question of how platforms navigate and evolve within such institutionally intricate and
9 regulated environments remains largely unaddressed (Essen et al., 2023). This gap becomes
10 even more pronounced when we broaden our investigation to include the transformational
11 entrepreneurship paradigm, as the experiences and characteristics of early-stage
12 transformational entrepreneurs that adopt the LSA and pivot. Consequently, it is needed for
13 both theory and practice to delve into the exploration of how transformational entrepreneurs
14 entry into non-platformized and highly regulated healthcare scenarios, overcoming its
15 challenges, particularly during the initial phases of platformization; this holds also true for the
16 investigation of how new entrants collaborate in co-creating value while facing institutional
17 pressures and conflicting logics, striving to establish legitimacy (Aerts et al., 2023; Essen et
18 al., 2023; Kulkov et al., 2023).

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23 Against this backdrop of scholarly gaps and evolving discourses, this study seeks to investigate
24 further the experiences and strategies utilized by early-stage transformational entrepreneurs
25 employing the LSA to navigate the digital healthcare landscape after the COVID-19, with a
26 concurrent examination of the role played by digital platforms and contextual conditions. Given
27 the rising popularity of experimentation and the LSA, this exploration appears crucial for both
28 theoretical development and practical application. The distinctive realm of healthcare can
29 represent a particularly fertile ground to test canonical theories and new frameworks, where
30 impacting boundary conditions may fluctuate throughout the LSA method's application,
31 predominantly shaped by factors including regulatory pressures, stakeholder relationships and
32 societal needs. Accordingly, from a theoretical perspective, it is an embraced opportunity to re-
33 examine boundary conditions and assumptions that we often take for granted, thus, to explore
34 entrepreneurs' role as "creators" and "discoverers" in the current "information-rich
35 experimentation-friendly" setting (Dushnitsky and Matusik, 2019, p. 441). Yet, it presents an
36 opportunity for the wide audience of entrepreneurs revolving around the healthcare sector,
37 since all the same must manage a significant influx of information and risk, while also
38 proactively striving under uncertain conditions that are not capable of measurement, often
39 without funding or under the head of restrictive regulatory frameworks and complexity
40 (Knight, 1921; Santos and Eisenhardt, 2009; Townsend et al., 2018).

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43 Accordingly, the research question is:

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46 **RQ:** How do early-stage transformational entrepreneurs relying on the LSA navigate
47 the digital healthcare space and pivot, overcoming resistance?

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49 Given the paucity of existing research and theories about the phenomenon, to address the above
50 expressed research question this study employed a grounded approach (Strauss and Corbin,
51 1990; Corbin and Strauss, 1990; Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Central features of this approach
52 (Bryant, 2017) are well-suited for addressing groups experiencing the same processes
53 (Langley, 1999), i.e., to comprehend how founders engage in the construction and
54 interpretation of their experiences (Gioia et al., 2013; Maysami and Elyasi, 2020) and,
55 complementary, how the sector's characteristics shape the same (Van Burg et al., 2022).

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58 **2. On the interplay between sector and entrepreneurs' characteristics: literature review**
59 **and conceptual framework illustrating investigation boundaries**

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Conducting grounded theory research entails a crucial initial step: comprehending and specifying the timing, scope, and depth of the literature review (Dunne, 2011). The engagement with existing literature occurred iteratively and contributed to enhance the research's quality while preserving inherent flexibility and openness of the method (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Given the need to locate the phenomenon in the highly regulated healthcare industry, sensitizing concepts were also used to provide guidelines for research in the specific setting (Blumer, 1954; Coffey and Atkinson, 1998; Bowen, 2006). In this regard, the conceptual framework outlining boundaries for the investigation (Figure 1) served as both a point of reference and a guide in this research. Additional sensitizing concepts in this study include "transformational entrepreneurship" and "liminality". Engagement with these two concepts took place iteratively, emerging after initial rounds of coding rather than from the outset, as in the case of "pivot".

Figure 1 visually presents the conceptual framework to foster understanding, incorporating multiple levels of analysis (e.g., Bradley and Klein, 2016): (1) the entrepreneurial level, (2) the task environment level (firm and ecosystem level), and (3) the macro environment level. The framework also depicts three stages of the pivot decision: (1) before the pivot, (2) enactment of the pivot, and (3) after the pivot decision. The resulting framework proves instrumental in guiding this research, as strategizing involves a multilevel series of activities and processes. Consequently, analyzing strategic choices and changes in the firm requires an examination, at different levels, of both the "inner" context (i.e., the inner environment of the firm) and the "outer" context (i.e., the economic, social, political, competitive, and sector environment in which the firm is situated) (Pettigrew, 1992, p. 9). This understanding also applies to entrepreneurship research, which is depicted as a multilevel phenomenon in the case of social entrepreneurship by Saebi et al. (2019), who highlight a shortage of contributions considering multiple levels of analysis concurrently.

To frame this interrelation between the inner environment of the firm and the outer context, different characteristics of the healthcare multi-stakeholders' ecosystem (Frow et al., 2016) have been integrated into the framework to reflect its distinctiveness. Indeed, scholarly discourse has embarked on delineating the contours of technology entrepreneurship within healthcare, encompassing the key traits of both entrepreneurship and the industry itself, thus heralding the establishment of a novel agenda (e.g., Kulkov et al., 2023). To chart a new course and overcome existent research limitations, there is the compelling need to better understand entrepreneurship in the healthcare systems in light of the sector's characteristics vis-à-vis entrepreneurs' characteristics.

2.1. Information leveraging and pivot in the early healthcare industry

As Fichman et al. (2011) closely pointed out, research anchored in the healthcare context should benefit from the integration of the sector's distinctiveness to evaluate how the same could inform the development of theory (e.g., Fichman et al., 2011). Healthcare is highly influenced by regulation, being also professionally driven and hierarchical. Along these lines, the strategic importance of information as a critical resource is emphasized since, compared to other sectors, the "idiosyncratic nature" of the healthcare industry requires specific information, i.e., significant institutional knowledge to research the sector and to seize the ever-growing opportunities and challenges generated by, e.g., the digital transformation (Agarwal et al., 2010, p. 805).

In the healthcare industry digital transformation is manifested by broad use of IT changing the provision of healthcare services, also leading a change in current processes and interactions (e.g., Kraus et al., 2021), along with the possibility to enter new or exit current markets

(Verhoef et al., 2021). It is widely acknowledged that digital transition and transformation have strongly contributed at least to a fundamental shift in terms of data and information availability; the same can now be viewed as a source of value creation for enterprises, not as a cost, as instead suggested by traditional economic thinking (e.g., Sampler, 1998).

Indeed, a central and leading theme of the innovation literature over the years has been that to develop successful innovation strategies, the role of information gathering and analysis appears as critical in entrepreneurial businesses (e.g., Varis and Littunen, 2010), also facilitating the “risk-taking and proactiveness dimensions” of entrepreneurs behavior (Entrialgo et al., 2000, p. 428), which use environmental data “to paint a mental picture” of their progress (Wood et al., 2014, p. 255). Entrepreneurial judgment, i.e., “purposeful behavior under uncertainty” (Foss and Klein, p. 91, 2012) plays a pivotal role in fostering the evolution of the decision-making process, navigating uncertainty and comprehending institutional forces (Foss and Klein, 2012).

Existent literature discusses how institutions can shape entrepreneurial action (e.g., (Dau and Cuervo-Cazurra 2014; Bowen and De Clercq, 2008). Developing an understanding about institutional forces at play and managing information appears crucial for entrepreneurs to scale up in the healthcare context. Consistently with entrepreneurship literature, “information acquisition methods” to reduce uncertainty can be classified into those focusing on predicting the environment and those concentrating on controlling it (Kuechle et al., 2016, p. 43). Prediction-based strategies involve using sampling techniques to estimate unknowns, while control-based strategies center on proactively shaping unknowns through proactive behavior. Yet, these strategies assume “different cognitive models of the situation” and “different degrees of involvement” by the entrepreneur (Kuechle et al., 2016, p. 44). Acquiring, framing, and leveraging information requires substantial time and effort and could be extremely challenging for early-stage entrepreneurs (Gans et al., 2019; Leatherbee & Katila, 2020), particularly in situations characterized by high levels of environmental uncertainty like in healthcare. To tackle this challenge, as introduced, a novel learning-oriented methodology, the LSA has gained prominence over the past decade among practitioners, becoming one of the most widely adopted entrepreneurship approaches to validate business models (Dushnitsky and Matusik, 2019; Leatherbee and Katila, 2020; Silva et al., 2021; Shepherd & Gruber, 2021).

Notably, one of the main pillar of this approach, i.e., the concept of pivot has garnered exceptional influence, largely entering the entrepreneurial lexicon, and embraced by incubator, accelerator and business schools programs around the world, as its evaluation and discussion against “perseverance” in response to rejection and adversities (Grimes, 2018; Dushnitsky and Matusik, 2019; Hampel et al., 2020; Shepherd & Gruber, 2021). However, only recently the concept began to receive growing attention from the academic community which provided, like the entrepreneurial community, different definitions from different perspectives (Hampel et al., 2020). It is quite clear that the pivot concept may be negatively affected by such a proliferation of meanings and lack of rigor, as underlined by Flechas Chaparro and de Vasconcelos Gomes (2021, p. 884), that by reconciling existent literature define the concept as a “*strategic decisions made after a failure (or in the face of potential failure) of the current business model and leads to changes in the firm’s course of action, resource reconfiguration and possible modifications of one or more business model elements*”.

Recent studies underline that while the term pivot is widely used, we still understand little about when and how entrepreneurial firms choose to make a strategic change and when such a strategic change constitutes a pivot (e.g., Bohn and Kundisch, 2020; Kirtley and O’Mahony, 2020; Sala et al., 2022).

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With regard to how entrepreneurs frame internal and external information to decide whether to pivot, several studies appear to provide insights on how the leverage of information by firms is intertwined with pivoting. Cumulatively, these studies offer insights into the role of information in a firm's pivoting, particularly concerning the relationship between entrepreneurs' information framing and their decision-making process regarding pivoting, which impacts the evolution of their strategies (e.g., Grimes, 2018; Kirtley and O'Mahony, 2020; Flechas Chaparro and de Vasconcelos Gomes, 2021; Sanasi and Grezzi, 2022). For instance, Flechas Chaparro and de Vasconcelos Gomes (2021, p. 896) identify 23 out of 86 papers of the studies' sample specifically suggesting that pivots occur because of new information about. Further, previous research also provides evidence about how pivot generally occurs in practice, i.e., when a strategic change becomes pivot and what could be the role information at this juncture over different levels. Kirtley and O'Mahony (2020, p. 4) found that pivot in firms is a result of multiple incremental decisions that accumulated into strategic reorientation over time. According to these authors, that consider the entrepreneur's framing of information as critical in the evolution of firm strategies, strategies evolved as decision-makers made "strategy exits and additions after new information acquired during the process of developing new innovations triggered strategic decision-making" (Kirtley and O'Mahony, 2020, p. 23). Similarly, previous studies also suggest that firms deploy pivot as a process, rather than an isolated event (e.g., McDonald and Gao, 2019; Ghezzi, 2019; Flechas Chaparro and de Vasconcelos Gomes, 2021; Sanasi and Ghezzi, 2022), where the firm start to rapidly collect information about the potential viability of the strategic reorientation (Sanasi and Ghezzi, 2022), e.g., by considering risks and uncertainties.

A very important distinction with regard to types of pivots is underlined by Hampel et al. (2020), who label early-stage pivots (e.g., Grimes, 2018) as "conceptual pivoting" and later-stage pivots they study as "live pivoting". According to Hampel et al. (2020), the dynamics underpinning each of them are very different. While early-stage pivots mainly occur in the minds of the entrepreneurs and relate to internal identity dynamics, in later-stage new ventures rely much more on external stakeholders and resources. In this second case, pivoting is far from a "cost-free" strategic option, since ventures face the key challenge of managing established relationships with resource providers who may be reluctant to accept the venture's shift.

Nonetheless, within the constraints of available information, our understanding still remains limited regarding how entrepreneurs' characteristics or sector's characteristics shape the LSA and decisions related to pivot in healthcare.

2.2. LSA, platform-mediated solutions and transformational entrepreneurship stance in digital healthcare spaces

In analyzing founders' responses to feedback and pivoting, Grimes (2018) asserts that enhancing the novelty and utility of one's ideas is influenced by both informational and identity constraints. Grimes (2018) contends that the founder's role is culturally situated, presenting two cultural conceptions: "visionary" and "scientific." The "scientific founder" role is reinforced over time through literature and artifacts, particularly the LSA. In contrast, the "visionary founder" role supports the narrative of persistence over pivoting in the face of negative feedback (Grimes, 2018). Beyond strict categorizations, Grimes (2018) suggests that future research should explore the evolving nature and connections of these roles and categories to deepen our understanding of the intricate reality of founders.

As previously mentioned, the LSA has predominantly been viewed as a one-size-fits-all solution, with potential boundary conditions often overlooked (Leatherbee and Katila, 2020; Silva et al., 2021), such as the variations when starting social ventures addressing societal challenges (Shepherd and Gruber, 2021). Certainly, the LSA has emerged as the predominant

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3 method employed by early-stage teams, frequently in conjunction with the development of
4 platform-mediated solutions. However, there is a lack of research on their application and
5 functionality in healthcare, a sector shaped by societal needs.
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8 The unique characteristics of the healthcare context imply that the transformational
9 entrepreneurship paradigm has the potential to complement the LSA. Indeed, transformational
10 entrepreneurship is a recently emerging notion for a phenomenon that arises from the
11 imperative to proactively cultivate impactful and efficient entrepreneurial activities aimed at
12 tackling global challenges such as unemployment, economic stagnation, climate change and
13 societal progress (Jones and Maas, 2019). In this regard, the proactive stance of
14 transformational entrepreneurship could be seen as an expression of change in the cultural and
15 symbolic dimensions of contemporary societies and could also be useful to understand digital
16 transformation (Ratten and Jones, 2018). While no studies have simultaneously addressed these
17 distinct research streams to date, various studies seem to validate our outlined premises and
18 objectives (e.g., Leatherbee and Katila, 2020; Shepherd and Gruber, 2021; Jones et al., 2023).
19 Comprehending the pace of transformational entrepreneurship and the responses of
20 transformational entrepreneurs within the healthcare ecosystem can yield substantial value
21 after the COVID-19. According to literature, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic has
22 undeniably acted as a catalyst, pushing the entire sector into a substantial integration of new
23 digital technologies across all processes, services, and management areas (e.g., Dal Mas et al.,
24 2023). Straightforwardly, the COVID-19 pandemic also heightens the urgency of leveraging
25 technology to bolster the sustainability of the entire system, which faces considerable strain
26 from escalating costs, a shortage of medical professionals, the necessity of addressing a
27 growing and aging population and patients with highly specific requirements (e.g., Kulkov et
28 al., 2023). The emergence of novel technologies, along with AI-generated insights,
29 advancements in telemedicine, and precision medicine, holds the potential to enhance patient
30 outcomes, ushering in a transformative shift in healthcare. This shift is characterized by
31 heightened efficiency, personalized approaches, and improved accessibility to healthcare
32 solutions (e.g., Garbuio et al., 2019; Hermes et al., 2020; Kraus et al., 2021; Dal Mas et al.,
33 2023).
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37 In the wake of these entrepreneurial, societal, and technological changes, startups are
38 growingly positioned to introduce innovative solutions that revolutionize the approach to
39 preventing, diagnosing, and treating health conditions through the integration of novel
40 technologies (Garbuio et al., 2019; Aerts et al., 2023). A cutting-edge example is the increased
41 development and diffusion of digital platforms within the healthcare sector “to leverage and
42 orchestrate a platform-mediated ecosystem to create and co-create value with a much wider
43 array of partners and actors” (Hermes et al., 2020, p.1). In this connection, a burgeoning body
44 of literature is also revealing the potential of digital platforms to facilitate transformational
45 entrepreneurship (e.g., Jones et al., 2023), especially in the aftermath of COVID-19 (Ratten,
46 2023). Accordingly, the example of digital platform is cutting-edge since the platform-
47 mediated ecosystem demonstrates the potential to assist early-stage transformational
48 entrepreneurs in addressing significant challenges presented by the intricacies of the healthcare
49 heavily regulated environment like, e.g., barriers to market entry, difficulties in expanding the
50 boundaries of the organization, or leveraging the stakeholders’ network and collaborations.
51 The proactive approach of transformational entrepreneurship, coupled with the adoption of
52 platform-mediated solutions, can shape how entrepreneurs perceive and leverage information
53 in a highly regulated and unpredictable environment, impacting pivot decisions. Indeed, despite
54 the sector’s characteristics, if entrepreneurs make change through choice, “taking seriously the
55 idea that choice matters ensures that it is the judgment and intent of the entrepreneur, rather
56 than haphazardness or passivity, that will shape the future of the start-up” (Gans and Stern,
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2019). At this juncture, platform-mediated solutions can serve as a catalyst for change (Essen et al., 2023) —despite consistent difficulties in entering non-platformized and high-regulated scenarios (Essen et al., 2023; Frishammar et al., 2023)— embodying valuable resources for transformational entrepreneurs and further facilitating socio-economic development (Jones et al., 2023). Notably, a digital multi-sided platform serves as the principal intermediary for transactions (of goods and services) and exchanges (of information and knowledge), fostering entrepreneurial innovation and value creation (Song, 2019).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework illustrating investigation boundaries and sensitizing concepts. Authors adapted from the contributions of Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 194 and Frow et al., 2016, p. 27.

3. Research methods

The grounded theory approach used, which entails understanding data within their specific setting (e.g., Corbin and Strauss, 1990) appears particularly suitable to offer insights around the ways in which the sector's characteristics and challenges can shape the entrepreneurial phenomena over different levels (Bradley and Klein, 2016; De Massis et al., 2018; Van Burg et al., 2022), as well as on how entrepreneurs respond to the same on the basis of their characteristics (e.g., Grimes, 2018; Van Burg et al., 2022). The purpose is to enhance theory development and overcoming limitations of existing literature by capitalizing on the context, i.e., on the sector's distinctive features and conditional background in which the events are embedded (e.g., Fichman et al., 2011; Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

As articulated by Bryant (2017), grounded theory encompasses three key features. Firstly, it is systematic, indicating that the research process and activities should follow a well-defined path, contingent upon contextual conditions and researchers' insights. Secondly, the prioritization of constant comparison of data is evident, with codes and categories forming the core of the method, and data gathering and analysis occurring concurrently. The constant comparison involves moving "between" induction and deduction (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 136). Thirdly, the iterative process permits new insights from each round of data gathering and analysis to propel the research toward a deeper understanding of concepts. Additional characteristics include specific coding procedures, memo writing, and theoretical sampling.

In the following sub-paragraphs, we provide a detailed outline of how this process unfolds in this study, addressing early coding and theoretical sampling (3.1), as well as issues related to data collection (3.3) and data analysis (3.4).

3.1. Early coding and theoretical sampling

The search for early-stage teams of founders operating in the realm of digital healthcare commenced in July 2022, and different open-ended interviews with entrepreneurs and key informants were conducted in the subsequent months. Initial coding enabled the identification of directions for further data gathering (Corbin and Strauss, 1990). Our specific interest lay in incorporating early-stage entrepreneurs who employ the LSA and aim to harness technology, specifically platform-based solutions, post-COVID-19 to address sustainability challenges in the sector with significant impact. Our focus centered on Italian startups, given Italy's status as a highly regulated market, reflecting traits typical of many industrialized nations, like also both the challenges confronting the market post-COVID-19 and the emerging opportunities within the Italian context.

After securing access, we opted for a rapidly growing Italian e-health startup with three co-founders, Easy Health S.r.l. (Benefit Corporation), which agreed to participate in the study in October 2022 (hereafter referred to as Easy Health). Initially conceptualized during a hackathon amid the first lockdown in March 2020, the CEO mapped out the "easydoctor" project to facilitate individuals in seeking medical attention and maintaining their health. The company, legally established as a Benefit Corporation in February 2021, pivoted from a previously developed mobile application for the business-to-consumer (B2C) market to create the first Digital Patient Engagement platform for healthcare—easydoctor. **It is noted that, although the entrepreneurs effectively developed the first mobile B2C application, the pivot occurred in the early stage of the venture, where relationships with stakeholders were only nascent.** The newly developed Software as a Service (SaaS) white-label platform integrates telemedicine features powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Medical Things (IOMT). According to the company's brand positioning statement, easydoctor is a secure, flexible, multi-touch digital patient engagement platform supporting healthcare professionals and facilities in managing people's health journeys. It facilitates easy and efficient data collection and enhances overall doctor-patient communication.

The present study relies on theoretical sampling, where data gathering is driven by theoretical reasons (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Corbin and Strauss, 1990; Sandelowski, 1995; Koerber and McMichael, 2008). Given the uncharted area of exploration and richness of the Easy Health case, to ensure efficient and effective saturation of categories, pattern direction and, hence, the highest "theoretical return" (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 202) the research ultimately focused on this single case study (Morse et al., 2002; Walsh et al., 2015).

The single case study approach is widely recognized and adopted in the literature concerning specific research questions, empirical settings, and when there is scarce prior knowledge of the phenomenon (Yin, 2014). This is particularly applicable in the context of exploratory research and when the unit of analysis comprises a group of actors (Yin, 2003). The grounded strategy employed aligns with this single-setting and single-case study approach, particularly effective when delving into a more microlevel of analysis focusing on individuals or groups experiencing the same processes, as observed in our case with the three co-founders (Langley, 1999, p. 700).

3.2. Data collection

As mentioned earlier, data collection for Easy Health commenced in October 2022 with the first open-ended interview (October 28th) involving the Marketing Manager and Co-founder. Table I illustrates the primary sample, providing a comprehensive list of interviews conducted with all three co-founders over more than a one-year period. The table does not detail all communications with the co-founders during this period, such as emails, telephone calls,

meetings, etc., as well as the activity of memo writing. All the interviews (Table I) were meticulously recorded and transcribed. The interviews took place virtually, through Google Meet and the open-ended questionnaire was administered through Google Forms.

We persisted in conducting interviews until we achieved theoretical saturation of the categories, reaching the stage in the research where gathering additional data appears 'counterproductive'—a point at which the 'new' that is uncovered do not significantly contribute to the explanation (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 136).

Over the mentioned time span, data have been collected and triangulated in different ways. Firstly, drawing on primary data obtained from interviews with the three co-founders (Table I), we ensure that each piece of evidence used in constructing the case is supported (triangulated) by at least two independent sources (Yin, 2003). Furthermore, we engaged in triangulate data collection by using different sources (Yin, 2003). In particular, we used open ended interviews, semi-structured interviews, open-ended questionnaires and structured interviews to gather primary data from the co-founders (Table I). Secondary data (Table II) was collected and analyzed to ensure the robustness of our findings over the three pivot phases and to avoid the loss of elements in the analyzed processes or other crucial details. For instance, secondary data proved useful in understanding the pre-pivot phase at the beginning of the research. Following Strauss and Corbin (1998, p. 51), we used excerpts from some secondary data for the pre-pivot period, more specifically Doc. 1, 2, 3, 7, 8, 9, 16 (Table II). Indeed, our interview approach commenced during the company's pivot enactment, allowing us to follow through the subsequent stages.

Despite being a venture with a founding team, every founder has been treated as a separate case to assess both individual and peer-group dynamics (Grimes, 2018). Consistent with Strauss and Corbin (1998), this is also discernible by following the adopted data gathering procedures and examining Figure 3 and Figure 4, which depict the data structure, with co-founders treated as a single unit of analysis to evaluate context/conditions (Figure 3), while incorporating data on strategic actions/interactions, thereby enabling consideration of peer-group dynamics through triangulation (Figure 4).

The early stages of the research were more open-ended, and later stages were directed by the emerging concepts, hence involving more strategic selection of informants and more structured interview protocols (e.g., Orlikowski, 1993). In detail, the early stages were mainly related to understanding the company characteristics, its value proposition, the key strategic choices and the main barriers to the business development. Then, as the concept emerged, and data were coded, new tags derived from literature were used (e.g., “transformational entrepreneurship”). Later stages were strictly focused on the pivoting of the company, i.e., before the pivots, enactment of the pivots and after the pivots, consistently with the narrative strategy employed. Indeed, drawing from the approach adopted by Sala et al. (2022), in the intermediate stages interviewees were informed about types of pivots and their main characteristics using the work of Ries (2011).

Table I. Primary data inventory

Respondent role	Primary sources and method	Period
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Interviewee 1 (She/her)	Marketing Manager & Co-founder	Unstructured interview (100 min.) Semi-structured interview (80 min.) Open-ended questionnaire (about 30 min.) Semi-Structured interview (60 min.) Semi-structured interview (50 min.) Structured interview (20 min)	October 2022 - November 2023
Interviewee 2 (He/him)	CEO & Co-founder	Semi-structured interview (70 min.) Open-ended questionnaire (about 30 min.) Semi-structured interview (35 min.) Structured interview (20 min.)	December 2022 - November 2023
Interviewee 3 (He/him)	Strategic Business Development & Co-founder	Semi-structured interview (60 min.) Open-ended questionnaire (about 30 min.) Semi-structured interview (30 min.) Structured interview (20 min.)	January 2023 - November 2023

Table II. Secondary data inventory

Source	Code	Type	Length
YouTube	Doc. 1	Interview (CEO)	42:53 min.
YouTube	Doc. 2	Interview (co-founders) for TEDx	39:05 min; transcription: 7 pages
YouTube	Doc. 3	Interview (SBD)	26:54 min.
Websites	Doc. 4	Web pages of easydoctor	-
PDF and documents	Doc. 5	Corporate Bylaws	10 pages
PDF and documents	Doc. 6	Corporate Bylaws	5 pages
PDF and documents	Doc. 7	Public posts of the CEO on LinkedIn	3 pages
PDF and documents	Doc. 8	Public posts of the MM on LinkedIn	1 page
PDF and documents	Doc. 9	Public posts of the SBD on LinkedIn	3 pages
Website	Doc. 10	Finance Community webpage	1 page
PDF and documents	Doc. 11	B Impact assessment	8 pages
PDF and documents	Doc. 12	Internal documents (strategic planning)	4 pages
PDF and documents	Doc. 13	PowerPoint slides (easydoctor presentation)	-
Website	Doc. 14	iBicocca webpage	1 page
PDF and documents	Doc. 15	Internal documents (project plans)	16 pages

PDF and documents	Doc. 16	New public posts of the CEO and SBDM on LinkedIn	2 pages
Website	Doc. 17	LifeGate webpage	1 page
Website	Doc. 18	Interview (CEO) for the Sole 24Ore Podcast	12:39 min; transcription: 3 pages.
Website	Doc. 19	Interview (CEO) for Forbes Italia, medtech panel	63 min. (panel session duration); CEO transcription: 2 pages.
Website	Doc. 20	Interview (CEO) published on the easydoctor website	3 pages

3.3. Data analysis

The emergent design of this research is marked by a sequential progression through various stages of data analysis, facilitating the transition from raw data to theoretical constructs. All data gathered were managed and coded through Taguette™, a free and open-source text tagging tool. We codify at the sentence-level (line-by-line), which takes us from mere description toward a conceptual mode of analysis. Except for line-by-line coding and the derivation of tags, which were assisted by software, the rest of the coding process was conducted manually.

In line with the grounded approach adopted, data collection, coding (Open, Axial and Selective cyclically), and analysis proceeded iteratively (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). More specifically:

i) Open coding was used to develop initial concepts and categories of information from all the data gathered (first order codes), that has been transcribed in a way suggested by the same data rather than imposed from outside (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). This allowed us to ground our study firmly in the phenomenon, also establishing a chronology of the venture's key activities around the three phases of the pivot and over different levels (entrepreneurial/firm, ecosystem, macro). This narrative strategy also served as an intermediary step between raw data and more abstract conceptualization in our research (Langley, 1999; Hampel et al., 2020).

ii) Axial coding, then, involved comparing similar first-order codes. In other words, the recurring themes served as the basis for identifying a set of cohesive and stable categories that linked together numerous associated concepts.

iii) Finally, selective coding involves refining the categories and themes into a final process model (Figure 5) accounting for tension between conditions and strategic actions/interactions of entrepreneurs. In other words, when seeking phenomena, our aim was to identify recurrent patterns of occurrences, events, or actions/interactions that depict the responses of co-founders to the challenges and situations emerging from the healthcare context in which they are situated.

Drawing from Corley and Gioia's (2004) depiction of qualitative data structures, Figure 3 and **Figure 4** illustrates the progression from initial first-order concepts, through second-order themes, to aggregate dimensions derived from our analysis (Gioia et al., 2013).

i) The final aggregate dimensions "Transformational entrepreneurship in healthcare" and "Complexity and information overload" denote conditions, encompassing sets of events or occurrences that, to some extent, elucidate why and how entrepreneurs respond in a certain way. Conditions may stem from various sources such as time, place, culture, rules, regulations, beliefs, economics, power, gender factors, as well as the social worlds, organizations, and institutions, along with personal motivations and biographies. These elements ("any one or all") are potential sources of conditions (Strauss and Corbin, pp. 130-131, 1998).

ii) Conversely, the final aggregate dimensions "Pre-liminal: information breaking strategies," "Liminal: information-based transition strategies," and "Post-liminal: knowledge-driven integration strategies" represent coding for evolving strategic actions/interactions—

“purposeful or deliberate acts taken to resolve a problem and, in doing so, shape the phenomenon in some way” (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 133).

Despite the visible tension created through our approach between conditions and strategic/action interactions, Figure 3 and Figure 4 remain static representations of a dynamic phenomenon. Figure 2 illustrates the adaptation and application of the analytic coding device proposed by Strauss and Corbin (1998, p. 184) which allows to locate the phenomenon in context, thus in building a systematic, logical and integrated account of the relationships between categories. The matrix indeed represents “constant interplay inter/action [process] with conditions/consequences [structure] and the dynamic evolving nature of events” (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 4). Figure 2 also illustrates the narrative strategies employed to trace a path and organize the data, i.e., by categorizing the period before the startup's pivot, its enactment, and aftermath over different levels (entrepreneurial/firm, ecosystem, macro).

Figure 2: Conditional/Consequential Matrix and narrative strategy employed

Figure 3. Data structure: **conditions**

Figure 4. Data structure: strategic actions/interactions over the pivot phases

Finally, it is underlined that the iterative nature of this study persists throughout the submission, review, and revision stages of the research process. Upon the completion of the initial version of this study and upon the completion of the current version, we conducted verification by sharing our findings with participants (co-founders) and engaging in peer debriefing with other researchers (Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

4. Research findings

This section establishes a chronological narrative of the research findings for Easy Health, tracing back to the initial efforts made by its founding members (e.g., Grimes, 2018; Hampel et al., 2020). The section's structure aims to progressively situate the reporting of findings related to the final process model illustrated by Figure 5 with a key focus on contextual conditions and the evolving sequences of entrepreneurs' responses, i.e., their strategic actions/interactions before the pivot, during its enactment and aftermath over different levels

(entrepreneurial and team-level, ecosystem level, and macro level). This aligns with the narrative strategy employed to trace a path and organize the data over the iterative phases of this study (Langley, 1999; Hampel et al., 2020). This section thus contextualizes the company's pivot within the full range of emerging macro and micro conditions. As discussed, the use of the Matrix (Figure 2) allowed a better grasp from the richness of the data and the complex interactions framed. In fulfilling its objectives, this section prominently features direct quotes from conducted interviews, contributing to a thorough contextual account of participants' experiences while zooming in on the different components of the final model (Figure 5). Accordingly, anticipating Figure 5 is expected to help readers place information and enhance their understanding (e.g., Gioia et al., 2022, p. 234).

Figure 5. Process model of transformational information crafting when pivoting

4.1. A glimpse into the context: the transformational stance of the entrepreneurs and initial efforts

At the most general level, exemplified by Fichman et al. (2011), the healthcare industry demonstrates considerable diversity across various dimensions, encompassing patients, professional disciplines, treatment options, healthcare delivery processes, and the interests of stakeholders such as patients, providers, payers, and regulators. This diversity is also evident in the Italian healthcare industry, primarily publicly oriented. In Italy, beyond regulating market entry, public authorities are also involved in the healthcare industry value chain by procuring new drugs, devices, technologies and evaluating the viability of innovative solutions for public healthcare facilities. One of the major challenges faced by entrepreneurs in this industry is the complex regulatory environment, which can slow down the pace of innovation and make the introduction of new products or services almost challenging. However, there have been recent efforts to streamline regulations and incentivize innovation in the sector, also as a

consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic that has led to a surge in the search for innovative solutions for the sector, benefiting from entrepreneurship. To the point the CEO and co-founder observed:

“From a certain viewpoint, the healthcare sector differs from other industries, particularly due to its distinctive regulatory and institutional framework. Healthcare professionals, like doctors, have this kind of role, like the one of the superheroes, that very often make the adoption of technological solutions and digitalization more challenging. However, I believe that digital tools can enhance and enable new services, rather than replace doctors. This shift towards digitalization in healthcare is reminiscent of what we have observed in the financial sector over the last 7-8 years since the introduction of PSD2, which opened up the financial market to new players. We are currently experiencing a similar transformation in the healthcare sector, especially after the COVID-19, with small players attempting to navigate the complex industry and develop their business models”.

As introduced, the entrepreneurs highlighted consistent cultural and organizational barriers found at the environmental level in relation to technology adoption and digitalization. In this regard, the marketing manager and co-founder (from here on, “MM”) also observed:

“In Italy the power is held by doctors. There is a strong block inside the industry. There is also a prevailing sense of distrust towards technology, which is not seen as a tool for facilitating their work, but rather as a potential threat to their activities. [...] Even patients very frequently prefer meeting doctors in person and exhibit reluctance towards relying on technology, also the simplest ones, like electronic health records. The issues and challenges we currently face are only expected to escalate, and this will inevitably require the incorporation of technology. For instance, as the number of sick people continues to rise, it becomes increasingly difficult to provide care for everyone due to the worldwide shortage of doctors. The burden on the healthcare system cannot be sustained without the integration of technology to alleviate the operational strain”.

The company's initial business-to-consumers (B2C) app allowed patients to upload their personal medical records and other health-related information, which could then be utilized jointly with the app's telemedicine capabilities. According to the strategic business development manager and co-founder (from here on, “SBDM”), the project was driven by a particular mission, that has remained the same throughout the years:

“The company was born with the intent to take care of the health of as many people as possible. This purpose has always been the same over time. The healthcare sector is so congested and bureaucratic. Healthcare should be something accessible to everyone. With a focus on the first technological product, the application was born as a B2C app”.

As mentioned earlier, our focus was on interviewing entrepreneurs embarking on social ventures within the healthcare sector, utilizing the LSA with the goal of harnessing technology to address sustainability challenges in the industry. The main characteristics defining transformational entrepreneurship, as emerging in the literature, include addressing sustainability challenges and proposing high-impact and technological solutions through novel and transformational entrepreneurial approaches. The co-founders visibly demonstrate their commitment to this transformational stance. For instance, in a long public post published on his LinkedIn profile, the CEO extensively described his experience in the healthcare sector and Easy Health mission focused on sustainability and value creation through the use of technology: “[...] *There is a new form of entrepreneurship, and I am glad to be part of it*” (CEO, Doc. 7). Initially, we were unaware of this **emerging categorization**, i.e., “transformational entrepreneurship”, relying more on the well-known categorization of “**social entrepreneurship**”. However, as we progressed through iterative coding phases and engaged with existing literature and collected data, we further relied **on** and developed this emerging categorization. This process allowed us to deepen our understanding of entrepreneurs' values and beliefs and their impact on responses within their specific operating context, particularly in challenging situations. In this regard, the SBDM observed: “*Personally [...] there is no one-size-fits-all solution. It's a matter of alignments, values, and approaches. The founder, or the initial founders, will always influence the culture and approach in the early stages of the startup. Their personalities will always shape the character of the startup.*” (SBDM, Doc. 16).

As reported for instance by the MM, they face persistent obstacles in the B2C market before pivoting:

“Over time, we have encountered a lot of doctors but eventually stopped attempting to engage in conversation with them as they consistently provided the same response: they could not proceed with any actions without the agreement of the strategic director of the organization. Doctors are not at fault for this. It's worth noting that this stance provides an intriguing insight into the extent of restrictions in Italy, because you may have people interested but they can't proceed and, therefore, they don't even want to listen and waste time.”

4.1.1. The origins of the project and the key role played by institutional actors

In June 2020, the CEO was approached by a prominent oncology organization in Italy involved in a telemedicine project. Despite the firm's initial lack of infrastructure to support the initiative, the director of marketing and technology enthusiastically encouraged the CEO to proceed. This introduction led the company to the first hospital in Europe exclusively dedicated to treating cardiovascular diseases. By December 2020, the hospital requested the company to sign a contract for developing an artificial intelligence-based project focused on cardiovascular disease prevention. According to the CEO:

“In December 2020 we were taken inside this hospital [name removed for privacy reasons] and they asked us to sign a contract. At that time, we did not have a registered company and, therefore, in only two weeks the company was constituted and then, legally registered. The meeting with the IEO that, in the following, took us to this hospital [name removed for privacy reasons] were two of the most important and key moments in the company life, giving our vulnerability at the beginning. Also, it has contributed over time to change our approach”.

Along these lines, it is emphasized that the initial mobile app was released on mainstream app stores but was later removed after approximately six months to pivot towards the platform. Engaging with the emerging literature on transformational entrepreneurship and platform proved highly beneficial in subsequent steps, contributing to the delineation of the data structure (Figures 3 and 4). This engagement significantly contributed to comprehending the entrepreneurial stance's role in tackling contextual challenges and complementing the standardized framework offered by the LSA through a systematic mindset. According to the CEO:

“When starting a healthcare-based startup, given the immense difficulties and complexities of the industry, the most effective way to progress is to make mistakes and learn quickly in order to move forward. We adopted this Lean approach, learning by doing and gaining insights from our mistakes”.

According to the SBDM:

“The platform we are currently developing has the potential to resolve numerous problems within the healthcare sector. The key challenge is to identify and address as many problems as possible, while also recognizing that it's impossible to tackle every challenge, as the healthcare system will certainly push you back. However, you have to be very fast in developing what is needed. [...]. If we had stayed in the B2C we probably would have died one year ago”.

As we navigate the iterative phases of this study, the complexity and information overload generated collectively by the healthcare context become apparent. As outlined in sub-section 4.2., these conditions were tackled at various levels concerning the pivot phases, as illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4, encapsulating them as second-order themes: regulatory maze, multi-stakeholder kaleidoscope, techno ambivalence, symbolic ambivalence, institutional actors as pathway pioneers, and resource-intensive demands. Entrepreneurs entering the healthcare sector confront challenges not only arising from stringent regulation and resource demands but also, despite emerging opportunities from digital transition, encounter technological resistance for both human and technical reasons (e.g., distrust and limited interoperability within hospitals). This technological ambivalence is further compounded by symbolic ambivalence driven by the imperative to generate profits in a sector where patient well-being should be the

primary focus. The transformational stance of entrepreneurs and the development of a platform, coupled with the adoption of the LSA, emerges as a pivotal element in addressing both technological and symbolic ambivalence in the sector, including resistance from institutional actors. Indeed, securing entry through institutional actors becomes a necessary step for these entrepreneurs.

4.2. Disentangling Easy Health's pivoting against the complexity of the sector and information overload

4.2.1. Before Easy Health's pivot and the reasons behind it (pre-liminal): information breaking strategies

i) *Entrepreneurial and Team-level.* To address the information overload generated by the specific healthcare context, the company's first MVP was utilized as a key tool to identify information streams at various levels and subsequently pivot towards the platform. To the point, the CEO exemplarily observed:

"By incorporating feedback from the stakeholders over time, we refined our product and experienced success during the application's development phase, as well as during the transition to the white-label platform".

At the outset, all of the co-founders were under 30 years old and lacked any specific medical competence or expertise, having graduated instead in the fields of management and economics. The entrepreneurs must rapidly identify challenges posed by the sector, breaking down information. In this regard, the SBDM observed:

"The decision to pivot towards the platform and B2B market was also driven, among the various factors, by our lack of medical expertise and trust-related issues. We recognized the numerous obstacles inherent in the medical sector, both public and private, including the challenges of dealing with lobbies and power dynamics not being medical professionals or part of the system. As a result, we realized the need to change our strategy, both for cash flow related reasons and the time requirements. We gained experience dealing with various digital transformation projects as consultants and we were able to leverage our young and enthusiastic team to support this pivot. [...]. We also made a pivot because to thrive in the B2C healthcare market, a lot of resources, both human and financial are needed."

The sharing and organization of information at the team level were prioritized by the entrepreneurs, who structured it around core themes. In this regard, the application of LSA served as a consistent foundation upon which they based their tailored approach to address the complexity and information challenges posed by the sector and pivot.

ii) *Ecosystem-level.* The MM highlighted the characteristics of the sales cycle of the healthcare B2C market and emphasized the importance of trust in this context.

"We decided to release the mobile app on app stores believing it would improve reliability and attract more customers during the sales phase. However, after several months, we discovered that customer perception hadn't changed significantly. In the healthcare industry, sales cycles are typically very long, and the app struggled to gain traction due to trust issues. Nevertheless, the first version of the app enabled us to conduct extensive testing and gain information and insights into how customers use it".

iii) *Macro-level.* The CEO discussed how the creation and value differs in the healthcare industry, and how pivoting towards a platform was deemed as helpful to overcome significant contextual constraints:

"Value creation in healthcare has unique characteristics that go beyond monetary gains. The impact of healthcare interventions extends not only to patients, but also to healthcare providers, as improvements in efficiency and effectiveness contribute to the wider community. The positive effects of these interventions are cumulative and create a virtuous cycle that amplifies their impact over time."

Certainly, within the distinctive traits of the industry and the associated information overload, entrepreneurs' proactive stance and adept execution of information-breaking strategies prove to be pivotal in expediting the necessary pivot and minimizing dissonance while preserving their vision. At the intersection between their transformational stance and the adopted LSA, we highlight mission-driven prioritization through confutation. During the pivot phases, the importance of information processing methods becomes apparent. These methods enhance control levels and provide a comprehensive understanding—through continuous and holistic focus— of the various interconnected avenues through which the entrepreneurs' purpose can materialize by generating and co-generating value within the systems.

4.2.2. Enactment of the pivot (liminal): information-based transition strategies

i) *Entrepreneurial and Team-level.* To implement the pivot the company analyzed information from the outside and used the feedback received to inform the decision-making process. Moreover, the company conducted weekly user experience tests involving patients, doctors, and other professionals, with the support of a dedicated UX designer and a team of software developers led by the CTO. The prioritization of users in such a way was also crucial to cope with the lack of medical expertise allowing to develop innovative solutions during the development process.

"We frequently base platform development decisions on feedback that we have received at least three or four times. We organized the way we disseminated outside information at the team level, basing it on themes like product, business development, and so forth. [...] Giving the platform logics, the knowledge and expertise in medicine and science is provided by individuals and organizations that collaborate with us. This does not impose any limitations. Our goal is to develop a technology-based solution that can simplify complex scientific information for patients, and act as a bridge between doctors and patients by providing services and using language that is easy to understand".

ii) *Ecosystem-level.* To execute the pivot and enhance their prospects, the company consistently engaged in proactive communication and collaboration with hospitals and regulatory agencies to gather information on regulatory requirements and customer demands. Additionally, the company reaped substantial benefits from its early involvement in the Talent Garden network—a European innovation platform and coworking network providing entrepreneurs across various sectors access to workspaces and training programs. This involvement facilitated valuable feedback, aiding in refining their platform and value proposition. Consequently, the company strategically narrowed down its target audience based on specific characteristics and prospects, formulating a strategy to cater to both the public and private sectors. To secure public sector projects, they navigate public bidding processes, while simultaneously engaging stakeholders through consultancy activities to make strides in the private sector. In this regard, the SBDM pointed out:

"The end-user has remained unchanged - the individual. However, to implement the platform, we had to redefine our target audience. Whereas previously we were targeting doctors and patients in a B2C approach, we shifted our focus to medical technology and pharmaceutical companies or private clinics with a certain scale to reach a larger number of patients. Consequently, we divided our strategy into two parts - public and private. In order to work with the public sector, we had to secure a public bid, which we achieved through the development of our platform. To engage with the private sector, we adopted a consultancy framework, as we call it, that enabled us to actively involve stakeholders and generate profits. [...] A significant portion of the proceeds generated from our consultancy services has been reinvested in the platform's development".

Further, when developing the platform, the company also opted for a "white label" approach as a means of addressing trust concerns in the healthcare industry. To the point, the MM observed:

"In May 2021, we chose to implement a white label approach, which entails displaying the name and logo of private clinics, pharmaceutical companies, hospitals, and similar entities on our platform's app. We made this decision because patients tend

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3 to have greater trust in their healthcare providers. Trust is a critical factor in the healthcare industry, and we recognized that
4 our app would not be widely adopted unless it was deemed trustworthy”.

5
6 During the implementation of the pivot, the entrepreneurs also extensively addressed the need
7 to become more vertically integrated and established key performance indicators (KPIs) and
8 other metrics. Nevertheless, the sector presented challenges in this regard, necessitating the
9 continuous provision of solutions that consider the diverse needs and flexibility of multiple
10 stakeholders. In this context, the MM exemplary was observed:

11
12
13 “The problem with our market is that becoming highly vertical is not easy. Those startups that have product metrics are the
14 ones that thrive. As for us, we have built a working method that has not yet been validated by the market at the product level.
15 Since we haven't been able to reach the market yet, we'll probably unlock it in September with [...], having completed the more
16 technological aspects. Then, we can indeed have those product metrics”.

17
18 *iii) Macro-level.* The pandemic has caused significant changes in dynamics within hospitals,
19 such as budgeting and decision-making, which have created new market opportunities and
20 impacted the development of the platform. In this context, entrepreneurs leveraged the potential
21 offered by platform-mediated ecosystems, particularly to respond endogenously to sector
22 exogenous challenges. Regarding this changeover driven by the platform implementation, the
23 CEO for instance observed:

24
25
26 “The most challenging aspect is the regulation of value distribution. Reimbursement is based on factors such as the number
27 of patient visits, which limits the potential to include a lot of additional features on the platform that we could include. Other
28 sectors may have lower value creation compared to healthcare, but it's simpler to capture their value. Nevertheless,
29 transitioning to the platform has facilitated the capturing of value in healthcare”.

30 4.2.3. After Easy Health's Pivot (post-liminal): knowledge-driven integration strategies

31 *i) Entrepreneurial and Team-level.* Easy Health won a national public bid to collaborate
32 through the platform with public HCOs and secured funding from a European-based bid. After
33 an increase in capital, at the beginning of 2023, it was also selected, along with 13 other startups
34 from around the world, to start a prestigious accelerator program. Over the years the team has
35 expanded, up to 12 members at the beginning of 2023, and encompassing various profiles to
36 cater to the emerging needs. As observed by the SBDM, mentioned changes brought important
37 challenges at the team level:

38
39
40 “Winning the public bid immediately required the ability to manage millions in a highly regulated and complex environment.
41 There was a change. Therefore, we placed a higher priority on hiring individuals with significant experience in the healthcare
42 sector and a proven track record of managing public funds, like a senior project manager. We prioritized these figures, rather
43 than experts in technology”.

44
45 *ii) Ecosystem-level.* After the pivot, the company persisted in integrating the platform's
46 potential through digital technologies, promoting co-creation mechanisms and value-capture.
47 For instance, leveraging the stakeholder networks while exploiting platform potential brought
48 the company, over time, to increasingly focus its attention on both developing ubiquitous
49 healthcare systems to offer both patient-centered solutions for a wide array of different
50 problems and sector specific challenges. In particular, entrepreneurs continuously integrate the
51 easydoctor platform to address privacy concerns, trust-related issues, interoperability
52 limitations, cultural barriers and high costs. As evidenced in Doc. 4 (Table II), the platform
53 employs this technology enabling healthcare professionals to autonomously create
54 personalized Digital Health Paths. Utilizing an API-based architecture, easydoctor seamlessly
55 integrates with leading EHR software and other applications, ensuring efficient interoperability
56 and data exchange. Aligned with Value-Based Health Care principles, easydoctor assists
57 healthcare professionals in measuring and improving health outcomes and patient experiences.
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3 Its multi-touch flexibility allows users to engage through various channels, ensuring a versatile
4 and user-friendly experience for both healthcare providers and patients.

5 Particularly, the proactive stance of entrepreneurs coupled with the implemented platform
6 allowed split up the strategy to target both public and private clients and increase margins.
7 Further, the pivot implied a broadening of the original product to include more features and a
8 change in the business architecture, from a low-margin, high-volume business to a high-
9 margin, low-volume. The company is also figuring out how to manage stakeholders' access,
10 usage, and monetization of data while enhancing stakeholders. To the point the MM observed:

11
12
13 *“The healthcare system predominantly focuses on chronic illnesses, which pose a significant challenge to the system.
14 Consequently, after creating the platform, we dedicated considerable resources to comprehending how we can provide aid to
15 patients, physicians, and pharmaceutical companies dealing with various types of chronic illnesses with very diverse
16 characteristics. [...] Regarding the empowerment of patients, there is a research concept that I cannot recall at the moment.
17 Until now, research has been based on clusters of individuals, and some diseases have been under-analyzed due to insufficient
18 access to data. For instance, women have several diseases that have never been fully understood because the majority of
19 studies have focused on white males. Having access to data is crucial for research.”*

20
21 *iii) Macro-level.*

22 At a macro-level, the SBDM exemplary observed:

23
24 *“The COVID-19 pandemic has not only made the digital transition and transformation more necessary but also accelerated
25 the process, leading the engagement of various public stakeholders into the platform easier and augmenting the opportunities
26 to receive financial support”*.

27 Nonetheless, challenges stemming from the sector's high regulation and lengthy sales cycles
28 persist as issues for the company, even after the platform pivot. For instance, stringent
29 regulation necessitated a knowledge-driven balancing of resource allocation between regulated
30 market fixed costs (e.g., high costs for certifications like ISO 9001 and ISO 845) and platform
31 development. To the point the MM exemplary observed:

32
33
34 *“[Removed for privacy reasons]”*.

35
36 In summary, after the pivot the entrepreneurs navigate these challenges by drawing upon
37 developed institutional knowledge, team capabilities, and leveraging the company's identity,
38 particularly in terms of “vertical flexibility” within the healthcare sector to address significant
39 uncertainties and risks. Entrepreneurs enhance their credibility and legitimacy by actively
40 participating in product development to showcase its safety and societal benefits. Concurrently,
41 they proactively engage with their stakeholder networks. The proactive stance shown in
42 employing technology, exemplified by the creation and integration of the platform, facilitates
43 the overcoming of multiple challenges inherent in the highly regulated healthcare setting.

44 45 46 47 48 49 **5. Discussion**

50 Our findings confirm unique challenges early-stage entrepreneurs encounter in the healthcare
51 sector, where information is recognized as a critical resource to manage, particularly amid the
52 industry's digital transformation. With regard to the LSA, largely portrayed as a one-size-fits-
53 all solution and probably the most adopted methodology among early-stage entrepreneurs to
54 validate business models, the concept of pivot holds centrality for entrepreneurial decision-
55 making in response to failure or potential failure. According to multi-sectoral literature,
56 acquiring, framing, and leveraging information is strongly intertwined with pivot. However,
57 our literature review reveals a research void regarding how entrepreneurs and sector's
58 characteristics influence the LSA and pivoting in healthcare, prompting an exploration into the
59 role of information at this critical juncture within this specific context.
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3 In analyzing founders' responses to feedback and pivoting, Grimes (2018) asserts that
4 enhancing the novelty and utility of one's ideas is influenced by both informational and identity
5 constraints. Beyond strict cultural categorizations ("visionary" vs. "scientific" founder role),
6 Grimes (2018) suggests that future research should explore the evolving nature and connections
7 of these roles and categories to deepen our understanding of the intricate reality of founders.
8 Indeed, entrepreneurs engaging with a type of identity work, specifically termed "decoupling"
9 by Grimes (2018), exhibited an appreciation of the scientific founder role without heightening
10 their alignment with it. We observed the same "mediated" identification among all three co-
11 founders from our sample with the "scientific" role, which allowed us to begin to shed light
12 on how their transformational stance complements the LSA in addressing societal challenges.
13 According to our findings, the different cognitive models and degree of involvement of
14 transformational entrepreneurs, yet their proactive stance in using technology to address
15 societal needs, complement the LSA in navigating the challenges posed by the sector. In this
16 regard, the systematic approach to information gathering and analysis facilitates the risk-taking
17 and proactiveness dimension of their behavior (Entrialgo et al., 2000), thus their focus on
18 proactively shaping unknowns through the same (Kuechle et al., 2016) and pivoting, while
19 maintaining the same vision. In turn, this fostered the evolution of the decision-making process
20 to navigate uncertainty and comprehend institutional forces at play (Foss and Klein, 2012), as
21 the healthcare environment requires the development of significant institutional knowledge and
22 specific capabilities to perform actions, i.e., to research the sector and to seize and address the
23 ever-growing opportunities and challenges. These findings hold particular significance in
24 digital healthcare, where pivoting unfolds as a liminal experience. From this case, we introduce
25 a process model (Figure 5) of transformational information crafting during pivoting in
26 healthcare. The resulting model and emerging theory present implications that validate, extend,
27 and challenge existing scholarship, also offering practical insights, as discussed below.

32 33 **5.1. Transformational information crafting, pivot and liminality in healthcare:** 34 **theoretical synthesis and implications**

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36 Section 4 provides a multi-factor account of company pivot (Flechas Chaparro and de
37 Vasconcelos Gomes, 2021) by contextualizing the same within the full range of emerging
38 micro and macro conditions before the pivot, during its enactment and aftermath. As discussed,
39 the arbitrary distinction between micro and macro conditions is arbitrary, focused on serving
40 theoretical purposes (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Accordingly, the employed methodologies
41 proved crucial in achieving the research objectives, enabling the consideration of both sector
42 (e.g., De Massis et al., 2018; Van Burg et al., 2022) and entrepreneurs (e.g., Foss and Klein,
43 2012; Grimes, 2018) characteristics in shaping entrepreneurial phenomena over different
44 levels. The final process model (Figure 5) accounts for this dialogical tension among the
45 different levels of the analysis, i.e., entrepreneurial/firm and ecosystem/macro (e.g., Bradley
46 and Klein, 2016).

47 48 *5.1.1. Pivoting as a liminal experience in healthcare: towards a process model of* 49 *transformational information crafting*

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51 The proposed model's final synthesis (Figure 5) indicates that pivoting in digital healthcare
52 unfolds as a liminal experience. The liminality of digital entrepreneurship in healthcare is
53 characterized by factors such as high regulation, multiple stakeholders, technological and
54 symbolic ambivalence, resource-intensive demands, and institutional actors acting as pathway
55 pioneers. These factors collectively contribute to an information overload and unforeseeable
56 uncertainty for early-stage entrepreneurs scaling up. Consequently, when early-stage
57 entrepreneurs face failure or the potential for failure and pivot, they effectively assume the role
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of liminality navigators within the sector/space to achieve the desired positioning. This implies that early-stage entrepreneurs in digital healthcare lack control over the outcome (beyond conventional risks), hindering their ability to capitalize on opportunities as in other markets. In this regard, their transformative stance in leveraging technology to address societal challenges becomes crucial for fostering the capacity to pivot in the healthcare context, supporting the same when obliged to adhere to paradoxical prescriptions like to be “stubborn”, yet “flexible” to scale-up, that create confusion as entrepreneurs navigate social demands (Grimes, 2018).

Our multi-level representation and engagement with liminality concept find robust support in the work of Henfridsson and Yoo (2014), who explore the liminality of trajectory shifts in institutional entrepreneurship. Expanding upon their insights, our study complements and broadens the understanding by incorporating the last decade's evolution in academic literature on pivot decisions and an explanation, stemming from recent advancements in transformational entrepreneurship literature, of the support provided by the transformational stance throughout the liminal transition in the specific healthcare context, characterized by unique features.

The concept of liminality, originally associated with the transitional states in a rite of passage, became a well rooted metaphor used across different fields. Introduced later in the research process, engagement with the concept of liminality, serving a "sensitizing" role (Blumer, 1954; Bowen, 2006), occurred after different coding rounds rather than at the outset. The entrepreneurs' notable uncertainty across phases, symbolic ambivalence, the metaphorical death concept expressed pre-pivot, and the imperative of securing institutional approval resembling a rite of passage guided by a master of ceremonies were primary indicators prompting the consideration of the well-established concept of liminality (Turner, 1969). Additionally, responses from entrepreneurs during distinct pivot phases began to emerge bundled into separation, transition, and integration, further stimulating our consideration of the liminality concept (van Gennep, 1909). Indeed, Turner (1969) defined liminality as a state between states, thus confirming van Gennep's nomenclature for the three phases of passage: pre-liminal (before the pivot), liminal (enactment of the pivot), and postliminal (after the pivot).

5.1.2. *Before the pivot (pre-liminal): role of information breaking and separation*

The final model (Figure 5) contributes a temporal aspect to the findings. This sequencing offers support for entrepreneurs in navigating liminality in digital healthcare through pivot. As discussed before, when confronted with failure and metaphorical “death”, transformational entrepreneurs proactively responded with pivot and becoming, according to our representation, liminality navigators.

Before the pivot (pre-liminal), at the entrepreneurial and firm level, our findings show the importance of understanding how entrepreneurs rearrange their priorities and update their beliefs to pivot due to internal and external information inputs, particularly when they are strongly dependent on a high-regulated environment and in the case of social ventures. The role of information in healthcare early-stage entrepreneurial pivot goes beyond just the identification of opportunities and challenges (e.g., healthcare regulations, reimbursement policies, patient privacy laws and other external factors) and varies across different levels of analysis; information at entrepreneurial and firm level represent a critical input for pivot and it involves the entrepreneur's ability to process, frame and leverage the same, that is based on prior knowledge, value, beliefs, experiences, cognitive biases and, as well, on firm's characteristics (e.g., size, age, team).

Sommer et al. (2009, p. 91) emphasize “active information searching” and “changing the course of action” based on emerging information as a fundamental approach for dealing with unforeseeable uncertainty in early-stage firms. Before the pivot, this manifested in the ability to proactively deal with resulting information overload. According to the findings, entrepreneurs' transformational stance, marked by an endogenous attitude in responding to

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3 various exogenous factors within the highly regulated environment, encompassed proactive
4 behavior, and enactment of the pivot over different phases heavily relied on their persistence
5 in facing the unknown. In the observed case, this attitude appeared to be significantly nurtured
6 not only by the initial accomplishments of the firms, as contended by Kuechle et al.'s (2016)
7 but, rather, by their ability to maintain a constant and holistic focus on the different and
8 interrelated ways in which their purpose could be realized and co-realized (or not) in the
9 healthcare context, thereby minimizing dissonance between preserving the same vision and
10 making one or more pivots to achieve a sustainable path to realize their vision.

11 Hence, regarding pre-pivot, our findings complement Wood et al. (2019), positing that
12 information about decision environments can significantly influence entrepreneurs' perceptions
13 of "(mis)alignment" between aspirations and established performance, impacting their pivot
14 decisions in the case of social ventures. The final model (Figure 5) expands on this perspective
15 and provides a phased view on how this stream of information impacts subsequent strategic
16 actions in the pivot, giving a more comprehensive understanding of the interplay among
17 information, entrepreneurs characteristics, and decision-making in the healthcare
18 entrepreneurial context.
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23 **5.1.3. Enactment of the pivot (liminal): information-based transition**

24 As underscored by previous literature with regard to highly regulated environments (Andries
25 and Debackere, 2006; Sommer et al., 2009), early-stage firms in healthcare encounter
26 substantial uncertainty stemming from the ecosystem and macro level that, however, goes
27 beyond conventional risks due to different and interconnected contextual factors. Shaping
28 organizational boundaries (Santos and Eisenhardt, 2009) becomes crucial, especially for new
29 technology-based firms, where there is the need to rapidly adapt the initial business model
30 (Andries and Debackere, 2006) and learn fast to mitigate potential significant financial losses.
31 In striving for optimal distinctiveness, compelled by contextual demands to flexibly integrate
32 vertically, the execution of a pivot is depicted as a condition of in-betweenness and confusion.
33 Entrepreneurs find themselves no longer aligned with the old and not yet integrated into the
34 new. In this phase, the entrepreneur's transformational stance supports them in leveraging
35 information (as discussed in pre-pivot) and persisting "to make things happen", even if they
36 can't traditionally capitalize on market opportunities and exert control.
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39 Given the depicted representation, where the attributes of the ecosystem significantly shape
40 entrepreneurial phenomena, such as institutional actors acting as pathway pioneers, high actors'
41 interdependence (Mahon and Murray, 1981), and a professionally driven orientation, practices
42 like strategic networking emerge in this phase, playing a key role. A growing body of literature
43 underscores how entrepreneurs engaging proactively with stakeholder networks can enhance
44 prospects and legitimacy (Vershina et al., 2020). Indeed, at the ecosystem level, networking
45 and communication offer valuable external know-how, information, and feedback crucial for
46 change and pivot, aiding in managing uncertainty and risks (Andries and Debackere, 2006).
47 However, the role of the network in mitigating external negative forces (Andries and
48 Debackere, 2006) is strongly inhibited in the healthcare environment. In this regard, technology
49 was seen as an enabler for transition and the development of the platform proved crucial, with
50 the first institutional actors signing contracts in the case observed, thus facilitating
51 transformational entrepreneurship (Jones et al., 2023; Ratten, 2023).
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55 **5.1.4. After the pivot (post-liminal): knowledge-driven integration**

56 According to our findings, platform-mediated solutions support early-stage transformational
57 entrepreneurs in tackling significant challenges during and after the pivot. These challenges
58 include barriers to market entry, expansion of organizational boundaries, and leveraging
59 stakeholder networks and collaborations to create ubiquitous solutions able to address technical
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3 interoperability issues and cultural barriers. Indeed, as from our findings, after the pivot, the
4 company persisted in integrating the platform's potential through digital technologies,
5 promoting co-creation mechanisms and value-capture, which is more difficult in healthcare
6 since the delivery of value is regulated. In doing so, the co-founders clearly demonstrate the
7 ability to exploit the sector-based capabilities developed at the team-level (De Massis et al.,
8 2018) and their identity. In this regard, some of our findings concerning the post-pivot phase
9 (Figure 5) and the dimensions of institutional knowledge exploitation and capabilities
10 hierarchies are particularly intriguing with respect to resource reconfiguration within the
11 industry sector. For instance, according to Dushnitsky and Matusik (2019, p. 442), traditional
12 hiring practices in startups once prioritized individuals with specific educational backgrounds
13 or industry experience. However, as these authors observe, in tandem with the prevailing 'lean
14 startup' trend, there has been a discernible shift, i.e., an increased emphasis on the importance
15 of experience in scaling-up and experimentation. While this emphasis was proven by our data
16 before the pivot, winning the public bid after the pivot immediately required the ability to
17 manage millions in a highly regulated and complex environment, leveraging institutional
18 knowledge specific to the sector. The co-founders placed a higher priority on hiring individuals
19 with significant experience in the healthcare sector and a proven track record of managing
20 public funds, despite the early-stage development of their platform-mediated solution and other
21 connected pressing needs. Having access to these resources proved crucial for providing the
22 potential for competitive advantage, with how they are integrated, combined, and deployed
23 being crucial to the shift towards the startup transformative phase (Figure 5).

24
25 Overall, the final model extensively addresses the reasons behind information's crucial role in
26 a healthcare startup pivot, aligning also with prior insights. In this connection, the study also
27 complements to what was contented by Sala et al. (2022), i.e., that the value proposition can
28 be sustained through pivoting, even in presence of significant constraints generated by the
29 highly regulated and institutionalized context. The healthcare sector's unique characteristics
30 make it an invaluable context to unravel the strategic importance of information and the
31 development of sector-based capabilities for scaling up. The final model dissects how
32 information gathering, framing, and leveraging intertwine with the risk-taking and
33 proactiveness dimensions that are integral to transformational entrepreneurship, allowing to
34 better understand entrepreneurial decision-making when employing the LSA for social
35 ventures addressing societal challenges.

5.2. Summary of study contributions: limitations, future research and policy recommendations

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37 The sensemaking of complex process phenomena like strategic change or, in this context, the
38 firm's pivot is more difficult since these are difficult to be represented through clear
39 classification or hierarchies, and also require to be interpreted throughout multiple levels of
40 analysis (Pettigrew, 1992; Bradley and Klein, 2016; Saebi et al., 2019). Thus, in this paper we
41 draw on a multi-level perspective to propose a final process model and an emerging theory.
42 Nonetheless, the paper is based on a single case that, although justified as a choice, always
43 requires caution when interpreting the results, particularly when attempting to extend them to
44 other contexts with different conditions. Our contribution aims for explanatory power rather
45 than generalizability, where explanatory power denotes "predictive ability"—the capacity to
46 elucidate potential outcomes in specific situations (Corbin and Strauss, 1998, p. 267). The
47 findings and grounded model thus serve as an initial empirical step toward a more in depth
48 understanding of early-stage entrepreneurship in healthcare amidst both the sector and the
49 entrepreneurs' specific characteristics. To this regard, the study firstly opens a meaningful

avenue, reinstating the focus on entrepreneurs' intentions and proactiveness in a context where an endogenous perspective has been mostly overlooked by the literature, still obscured by a predominant –but superficial– coverage on exceptionally arduous exogenous constraints that negatively impact entrepreneurial action in this sector. Accordingly, there is the connected opportunity to advance our understanding on transformational entrepreneurship impact regarding both decision-making level and social value creation in healthcare, a sector where identity, relationships with stakeholders and legitimacy-related issues can wield substantial sway. Indeed, aligned with Bjørnskov and Foss (2016), our findings also confirm how emphasizing the healthcare institutional context and its impact on early-stage entrepreneurship enhances our explanatory capacity regarding entrepreneurial decision-making.

The study's findings enrich and extend the existing literature in multiple dimensions –also beyond the specific objectives of the paper– by providing a grounded foundation for carrying out more comprehensive inquiries in future research. Empirically, this study appears to be the first multi-level analysis dedicated to comprehending early-stage startup pivots and the role of transformational entrepreneurship in addressing societal challenges within the healthcare sector. We had the exceptional opportunity to verify the findings by triangulating all the data, as all three co-founders participated in every strategic decision, sharing information and cooperating from the very beginning. However, given the multitude of factors that can impact the pivot of a company over different levels, additional field studies in healthcare would be extremely valuable, particularly if addressing issues regarding sector-based entrepreneurial capabilities (e.g., De Massis et al., 2018) and later stage new ventures that rely differently on external stakeholders compared to early-stage ones (Hampel et al., 2020). Future research has also the opportunity to test the boundaries of the final process model in both healthcare and other highly regulated contexts. Moreover, by advancing our understanding on platform-mediated solutions, the study contributes to the burgeoning literature highlighting how technological revolutions can reshape firms' value co-creation in B2B service systems, even within regulated sectors like healthcare (Breidbach and Maglio, 2016; Leone et al., 2021). Institutions, as noted by Bjørnskov and Foss (2016), shape entrepreneurial activities and may guide them towards productive, rather than unproductive outcomes. This has been observed in our case, aligning with a view seeing regulations as a possible catalyst for "new and (sometimes) unpredictable avenues for value co-creation and collaboration" in the innovation landscape (Schiavone and Simoni, 2019, p. 1609).

In parallel, a further understanding is advocated regarding social value creation through entrepreneurship in healthcare. For instance, Saebi et al. (2019) noted in the multi-sectoral realm of social entrepreneurship that while there are numerous instances in the literature showcasing successful social ventures and the achievement of specific economic and social objectives, there is limited understanding of transformational mechanisms during the post-venture formation stage. Specifically, according to Saebi et al. (2019), there is a gap in knowledge regarding whether and how the success of various social ventures truly leads in creating additional value or merely in reallocating value between stakeholder groups, or from one venture's stakeholders to another. In this regard, we can only underscore the same need concerning entrepreneurship in the specific context of healthcare.

Our study can also have significant policy implications for healthcare entrepreneurship. In recent decades, particularly post the global financial crisis and COVID-19, substantial funding has been directed towards business and education policies, covering regulatory measures, formal education, and professional training for individuals establishing new ventures. Based on the study's findings, the effectiveness of these interventions may be significantly compromised without a context-appropriate business approach accounting for the diversities

of the healthcare sector. Policies tailored to the unique identity and specificities of the healthcare sector can yield high returns, especially in pro-market institutional contexts (e.g., Dau and Cuervo-Cazurra 2014) and better allocation of entrepreneurial efforts and resources (e.g., Bowen and De Clercq, 2008). Consequently, to advance understanding and policy debate, future contributions should focus on this distinction by considering the diversity of the sector. Comparatively, Hidalgo (2015, pp. 153-154), for instance, vividly looks at and traces this distinction as the difference between the idea of "stock," commonly used in aggregate models of economic output and growth, and the idea of "diversity", that is crucial to honoring Leontief's advice to preserve the identity of the elements involved in economies, even when considering knowledge and know-how. Illuminating the path forward, our study only shed some light on some key elements in healthcare that have the potential to both positively and negatively influence early-stage entrepreneurial phenomena. The realization of these beneficial or negative outcomes still remains a large unaddressed issue by literature.

Declaration of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

First author: Conceptualization; Methodology; Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing - Original Draft; Writing - Review & Editing; Visualization

Second author: Investigation; Supervision

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